

**THE ISSUES OF YOUTH EDUCATION AND THE GLOBAL OUTLOOK
OF AJINIYAZ KHOSIBAY ULI**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11195742>**

Abstract: This article tells about the religious direction of Sufism, mainly the doctrine of Sufism suggests that it has a great influence on the historical and cultural, mainly spiritual development of all mankind, on the prosperity of civilization.

Key words: social, philosophical, cultural, civilization, influence .

Ajiniyas believed in Sufism and paid great attention to humanism; this can be seen from his equal treatment of people of different ethnic origins and religious denominations. The poet brought up the issues of tolerance in religion as he believed that according to the Tasawwuf doctrine not only the followers of Muslim religion but also the whole humanity is valuable. In his poem “Dildarym” (My Beloved) he also analyzed the social circumstances in other countries and said: “Muslims are being burden to Russia” [4:15] which is a clear proof of it.

According to the poet neither religious nor national differences can prevent peoples from making friends with one another and having fraternal relations. Proceeding from this idea, in his work “Demishler” (They Say), he said respectful words about the prophet Jesus Christ and his mother Mary, the book Evangel and Jews, and underlined that even if peoples belonged to different religions, they were created by God and have one and the same source of origin. Saying, “We are human being of one origin,” he put forward the idea that religious differences must not generate unpleasant ideas among humans. He asserted that not only will the common people suffer, but also the clergy who belong to Sufism doctrine and dervishes travelling from village to village suffer heavily if the Padishah rules the country dishonestly as a dictator. He warned that the mullahs who did not tolerate the despotism started to look up in the holy book the regulations of the Sharia, and the devout followers of Sufism denomination were also suffering hardships from dishonesty of the Padishah. He also criticized some padishahs¹ who spared neither rank and file nor the religious people who belonged to Tasawwuf teaching.

According to the logic of the thinker’s poem “Demishler” (They Say) Sufism is being in love with God, choosing the way which leads to the Creator by devoting one’s life wholly to God. This doctrine means understanding and loving God with

the help of one's soul's feelings, shrewdness of soul, and internal spiritual experience. Therefore, Sufism is the doctrine which explains that the love of God is understood little by little, by enlightening the soul, but not the phenomenon which can be seen and observed directly and listened to in order to understand. Because "The doctrine against God will disappear" [4:98]. On the basis of his belief in the world relying on Tasawwuf doctrine, the poet spoke against the social inequality of his time, dishonest ruling of the state, invading of one country by another and strictly criticized such activities in his poems "Bozatau" and "Analar" (Mothers). According to Ajiniyaz, the Lord created man clever, advanced, ready for most trials of life, and capable of learning secrets of nature. It is wrong of a man created perfectly to be dull and cruel. God endowed him with the ability to work using his wisdom. Taking into consideration this fact, the poet said that no one in the world has the right to be conceited, to vent his indignation on others, to bend them to his will and make them follow his commands, to force them to withdraw their words, and make them do what they do not want to do². Such people are considered to be against the Creator, and having contributed to making evil and cruelty on the earth. Therefore, Ajiniyaz argued against social inequalities, the despotism of padishahs and noblemen in his poems "Endi" (Now) and "Bozataw". He brought up democratic and humanistic issues stating that all humans are equal before God, human rights of people cannot be higher or lower, but equal, one must treat the poor, the weak and orphans humanely. "Everyone was not equal," he said in his poem. Thus, under the influence of Sufism, the poor layer of the population started to strengthen their social status. Moreover, Sufism was close to farmers' and cattle breeders', craftsmen's and educators' and ulema's everyday concepts, and their goals for the future. Sufism doctrine is important not only in the Islam world, but also in the whole world. It has had a great role in the historical-cultural, especially, spiritual development, and thriving of the civilization of the whole world. It spread education, science and enlightenment activities among population, deepened the content of the ideas of humaneness and others conceptions. It has had a great impact on people's spiritual thinking, mode of life, education, customs and traditions and complemented their content. It also served a great deal in improving people's self-consciousness, in putting in order their social life and lifestyle. In fact, the main idea of the Sufism doctrine was ensuring the humanity to reach full happiness, its mastering of the real humaneness taking example from religious and human values. Admitting these requirements and directions of Sufism as a source for his views, Ajiniyaz became

a great Karakalpak poet and thinker and managed to develop the Sufism doctrine further using it creatively.

References:

1. (1960). Ajiniyaz. Selected works. (p.180). Nukus: KKMB.
2. (1965). Ajiniyaz. Selected works. (p.295). Nukus: "Karakalpakstan".
3. (1975). Ajiniyaz. Selected works. (p.252). Nukus: "Karakalpakstan".
4. (1988). Ajiniyaz. Selected works. (p.152). Nukus: "Karakalpakstan".